

SOCIAL SCIENCES

TRANSATLANTIC RELATIONS FROM THE CRITICAL THEORY PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Critical perspectives oppose neorealist and neoliberal schools of thought which focus their attention on state and international organizations, viewed as the main actors in the international system, and offer the alternative to shape the society and the world based on the individual characteristics. Critical theorists advocate self-awareness, resistance and engagement in the social and political life to prevent and counter any form of domination from any political or social actor. Identity, equality of gender and race, and climate change are among the main concerns of critical theory supporters who advocate the importance of ideas at the expense of concrete elements of power and economics.

Based on this theoretical framework, we intend to identify the elements that associate the United States and the European Union to critical theory and its related perspectives and to evaluate their impact on the transatlantic relations.

Keywords: critical school of thought, reflectivism, constructivism, feminism, human rights and individual freedoms, climate change, the European Union, the United States.

Introduction

Critical perspectives, also referred to as radical theories have appeared relatively recently as a reaction to the neorealist and neoliberal schools of thought, which are considered to have common approaches that entitle their integration into the paradigm of *rationalism*. Originating from the Latin word *ratio*, which means reason, rationalism is a philosophical school of thought and a method of thinking that advocates reason as the only way to discover the truth regarding the way the surrounding world functions.

Critical theorists reject the basis of neorealism and neoliberalism, according to which states are rational actors motivated by interests, the international system is anarchic, and internal factors have a reduced influence on the dynamics of the international arena. On the contrary, they advocate that other actors than states influence international environment, namely the people whose actions are based on the perception of their own person and the perception of the surrounding environment. Thus, critical theorists sustain *reflectivism* (term made popular by Robert Keohane) as an alternative to rationalism, a perspective that puts the individual consciousness, the self-perception and the perception of the surrounding world in the center.

Critical perspectives

Frankfurt School for Social Research has developed the critical theory as a school of thought. One of the founders of the critical approach, Herbert Marcuse, rejecting both the communist and capitalist society patterns, promotes the return to individual and individuality, seen as a manifestation of human freedom and a means to achieve progress. In one of his landmark

books "*One-Dimensional Man: Studies in the Ideology of Advanced Industrial Society*", Marcuse criticizes the existing different forms of oppression in communist society, as well as the consumerist approach specific to capitalist society. He emphasizes that these manifestations limit the individual to being a part of a system of thinking and of a pattern of behavior that negatively affect the individual by eroding his capacity of critical thinking.

Marked by profound pessimism, Marcuse takes a revolutionary attitude and proposes the rejection of all forms of control on the individual.¹ On the same note, Marcuse encourages nonconformism and disobedience of the social limitations in his book "*Eros and Civilization: A Philosophical Inquiry into Freud*" in which he focuses on human instincts, evoking the necessity to use them as a basis to shape the society. He advocates that such endeavor can be realized by transposing the demands in the political domain and sustain them with perseverance to the political decision-makers.²

A major contribution to the critical theory development also had Max Horkheimer, who approached in a profound critical manner topics like authoritarianism, economic crisis, mass culture and environmental agenda. In his landmark book "*Eclipse of Reason*", Horkheimer emphasizes the relation between subjective and objective concepts of reasoning which, in his view, are associated with the reflections on spirit and nature, subject and object³. Horkheimer added the instrumental dimension of reasoning to the subjective and objective concepts, and observed the de-evolution of states from the behavior based on objective reasoning, which is directed towards result and is considered the

¹ Douglas Kellner, Introduction to the Second Edition. Herbert Marcuse, *One-Dimensional Man: Studies in Ideology of Advanced Industrial Society*, p. xi, London, Routledge, 1991.

² Herbert Marcuse, *Eros and Civilization: A Philosophical Inquiry into Freud*, pp. xi, xxv, Second Edition, Beacon Press, 1974.

³ Max Horkheimer, *Eclipse of Reason*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1947, p. 173, Internet Archive, accessed at <https://archive.org/details/in.ernet.dli.2015.59625/page/n161/mode/1up>.

only solid ground to view the world, to the behavior based on subjective reasoning, which erroneously focuses on means at the expense of result, to the behavior based on instrumental reasoning, which puts the utility value in the center of preoccupation.

Erich Fromm⁴ brings attention to freedom, viewed as a characteristic of individual nature, but also as means to perceive and understand the world. In his view, there are two types of freedom: *negative freedom*, achieved by emancipation and overcoming social conventions, and *positive freedom* that involves the capacity to act within the society and to influence the society.

The main theories derived from the critical approach are *constructivism* and *feminism*, both advocating for the replacement of elites, viewed as corrupt and abusive, and the development of autonomy, while putting the individual in the center.

Constructivism is based on the idea that the process of knowledge and understanding the world represents the result of individual interpretation and individuals are influenced by the cultural, historic, social, and environment context. Therefore, the self-perception, the perception of the environment and the perception of the world represent the sum of the contexts surrounding and influencing the individual.

Constructivist supporters (David Held, 1980; Jim George, 1994; Lynne Rienner, Boulder, 1994; Christian Reus-Smit, 1999; Martin Weber, 2014) encourage increasing self-awareness and individual freedom, as well as enhancing the social role of the individual to protect against any manifestation of power from the state, institutions or other social groups, which limit knowledge and evolution, regarded as a construction process. Profoundly marked by the perception of the risk of domination, promoters of the constructivist theory insist upon knowledge as a means to achieve the capacity to resist and to oppose any domination or constraint tendencies from predominant groups or state institutions, who are considered to possess the power to impose their will and influence knowledge and social construct.

Identity, interethnic conflicts, global warming, equality of gender and race are among the main preoccupations of the constructivists who advocate the importance of ideas at the expense of material elements of power and economics.

Encouraged by the end of Cold War, which seemed to end the dominance of realist approaches, critical school of thought focused on new themes of reflection, exploring diverse ideas of the social and political life and paying a particular attention to identities and the subjective dimension of individual.

Developments related to globalization, such as the unprecedented extension of markets, the technological advance, the spread of values and the diversity of social behavior patterns are regarded by the critical theorists as enhancers of the global political association, beyond

the rigid framework of the international norms and institutions.

Critical theorists consider that, due to its important role for different actors globally, the international normative framework erodes the relevance of Westphalian system of nation-states and the legitimacy of state in exerting its prerogatives. Thus, the supporters of critical theories partially credit the theory of Samuel Huntington on the *clash of civilizations*⁵ and the assumption that the big division and the main cause of conflicts worldwide would be of cultural origin. However, Huntington does not deny the importance of states, contrary to the critical theorists who strongly reject this approach.

Some critical approaches attribute the responsibility of states' behavior and actions to the leader as they consider that particular personal characteristics of state leaders, linked to the behavioral typology, the environment of their origin and of their evolution, family origin or persons with whom they related, all these factors influence the manner the leaders approach the international agenda. Thus, it is evoked that the decisions and actions of a state represent the effects of personal characteristics of the leader and not the result of reasoning.

The feminist school of thought based its development on the inequality of men and women and the dominance of men over the main fields of activity within the society. This state of fact was considered by the *feminism* pioneers and later by the feminist exponents and theorists to be the result of patterns deep-rooted in the society, which had to be eliminated.

Aside from countering this state of fact by the promotion of gender equality, the feminist school of thought brings attention to the pacifist approach as an alternative to the realist approaches, thus changing the perspective from the power of coercion to the power achieved by peaceful gathering of individuals to promote cooperation and development.

Feminists credit the idea that increased involvement of women in the management of international affairs will infuse a stream of openness towards peace and will lead to the erosion of masculine approaches developed around the idea of power in its material and military sense, stimulating understanding and cooperation for peaceful purposes with positive effects on the mankind.

In the early stages of the development of the feminist school of thought, feminist pioneers explored and build on the literary writings of women authors, emphasizing the feminist style, symbolism and perspective on life and the evolution of society. The book „*Encyclopedia of Feminist Literary Theory*” in which feminism is defined as a conglomerate of political and social ideas caused by the fact that gender inequality continues to be a pressing difficulty in the contemporary society⁶ is representative for the feminist school of thought. Against this background, it became necessary

⁴ Erich Fromm, *Escape from Freedom*, Farrar & Rinehart, SUA, 1941.

⁵ Samuel Huntington, *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order*, Simon & Schuster, SUA, 1996.

⁶ Elizabeth Kowaleski Wallace, editor, *Encyclopedia of Feminist Literary Theory*, Preface, p. vii, Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, London, New York, 2009.

to develop an activist agenda to counter this state of affairs.

Feminism evolved in three phases. In the first phase, covering the period of the 19th Century and the beginning of the 20th Century, feminism focused on achieving essential rights for women, such as the right to vote and access to education, at the same time, arguing for the improvement of labor and life conditions for women.

The second phase, covering the period of 1960 – 1980 brought the attention of feminist supporters to the cultural and political inequalities, as well as to different forms of discrimination within the society. In this context began the struggle to eradicate all these disparities in Europe and the United States. During this period, feminist introspection and reflexive approach reached new dimensions, stimulated by the emancipation of women and the achievement of aspirations by active involvement in all types of social, political and economic life.

The third phase, started in the '90s and currently in progress, aimed initially at pursuing the agenda of the previous phase, having as main objective the achievement of gender equality in all domains of activity and social and political manifestations but in time, has extended to the activism against oppressive actions against masses and race-based groups. This period is largely known as the *women's liberation*⁷ period when a series of women's social movements appeared and became visible in the Western world. This period in the evolution of feminism brought to attention new approaches, in line with the Frankfurt critical school of thought, which drives its analysis from the perspective of the social impact of the dominant ideology, as mentioned before.

This is the period when demands regarding increased representativity of women in the political, social and cultural domains has grown and has become more energetic, while feminists strongly opposed the patriarch approach of education, policy and economy agenda. Starting with the 2000's, the topic of sexual orientation and gender identity have become increasingly visible within the society, as well as on the political agenda.

Critical perspectives as a transatlantic bridge

The same as liberal and realist schools of thought, critical school of thought originated from and developed in the United States and Europe. But much more than the first two theories, which were assimilated and applied globally by numerous state and non-state actors, critical theories represent eminently a Western

theme that manifests itself completely only in the United States and Europe.

The European Union and the United States fully sustain, protect and promote individual freedoms and pay a particular attention to the individual autonomy, therefore both actors can be associated to critical theories, which are currently on the rise within both the American and European societies.

The freedom rights are at the core of the Constitution of the United States. The first amendment of the *Bill of Rights* guarantees the right to religion, freedom of speech, the right to peaceful association and the right to address the authorities in order to correct any injustice perceived by any citizen.⁸ The following amendments cover the citizens' rights to individual safety and possession of goods, as well as the right to private property. The right to a correct treatment and a just trial under the law is largely covered by four of the ten amendments of the *Bill of Rights*.

At the same time, the individual rights and freedoms play a fundamental role in the European Union's build-up and they are essential for the development of the EU. Originating from the cultural and humanist European legacy, individual inalienable and inviolable rights of freedom, equality and rule of law have a central role in the *Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union*⁹ and they are enhanced in the *European Convention on Human Rights*¹⁰ and the *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*¹¹. Moreover, European citizens' individual rights ensured by the Constitution of their originating democratic states, such as the right to freedom, freedom of speech, the right to association and state protection, the right to correct justice and to defend individual freedoms and interests etc., are supplemented by the EU rights of free movement and residence on the EU's territory, the right to vote and be elected within the EU, as well as the right to petition.

In addition to the internal legislative framework that guarantees individual rights and freedoms, both the European Union and the United States are profoundly attached to the *International Law of Human Rights*, which includes the *Universal Declaration of Human*

⁷ Ruth Moulton, *Psychoanalytic Reflections on Women's Liberation*, Contemporary Psychoanalysis, 1972, Volume 8, no. 2, pp. 197–223.

⁸ Bill of Rights of the United States of America (1791), The Bill of Rights – Full Text, Amendment I, Bill of Rights Institute, accessed at https://billofrightsinstitute.org/e-lessons/bill-of-rights-of-the-united-states-of-america-1791?gclid=CjwKCAjwov6hBhBsEiwAvrvN6ACe9RyNUAl6m0xTlck7nlcpRVZ77uwlcnSQWteyi9Pih0idBRqy-hoCdtkQAvD_BwE

⁹ Official Journal of the European Union, Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union, C326/15,

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¹⁰ Council of Europe, European Court of Human Rights, European Convention on Human Rights, Strasbourg cedex, accessed at https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/d/echr/convention_eng.

¹¹ Official Journal of the European Communities, Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2000/C 364, accessed at https://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf

*Rights*¹², the *International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights*¹³, and the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*¹⁴.

Furthermore, shared democratic values of individual liberty, human rights, democracy and the rule of law strongly connect the United States and most of the European Union member states, which are also NATO members, as they commit in the *NATO Strategic Concept 2022* to safeguard them, to protect human security and advance *Woman, Peace and Security* agenda. At the same time, NATO members affirm their strong commitment to the purposes and principles of the *Charter of the United Nations*.

Topics promoted assiduously by the supporters of critical school of thought, such as global warming, gender equality and equal opportunities, identity manifestation in all its forms, social tolerance, minorities protection, domestic security and environmental agenda, all these themes are high on the US' and the EU's political and social agenda to the same extent. They also represent a solid bridge between the US and the EU that facilitates the transatlantic cooperation, as reflected by the good relations between the American and European communities.

In the Statement of the US – EU Summit in June 2021, *Towards a renewed Transatlantic partnership*¹⁵, both parties affirm, among other things, their strong support for and engagement in preserving the climate and the planet, and state as common objectives to protect the planet and sustain the green development and to consolidate democracy, peace and global security.

Aside from the temporary withdrawal of the US from the *Paris Agreement* during Trump Administration, causing profound annoyance to the EU, the United States and the European Union are currently the main supporters and promoters of the initiatives and measures designed to manage responsibly climate change. In this endeavor, the EU and the US make use of any opportunity to raise awareness of the topic globally and advance it on the international agenda in order to gather an extended support from state and non-state actors to significantly influence the world and generate the positive effects needed to manage effectively the global challenge of climate change. Moreover, both the European Union and the United States offer clear examples of responsible behavior in economic, energetic, technological and social domains and they commit to implement and sustain the implementation by other parties of the *Paris Agreement* and the objectives assumed at the UN Climate Change Conference – COP 26 in 2021.

In practical terms, the US package of measures designed to manage climate change challenges together with the public health and social measures totals approximately 2 trillion USD and is largely supported the

American society. EU has also set an ambitious agenda in this domain targeting a reduction of at least 55% of the carbon emissions by 2030, in the perspective of reaching climate neutrality by 2050, and is ready to supplement its investments to up to 113 billion EUR in order to achieve this aim.

Also, significant progress has been made in the EU legislation and normative domain of climate change and green transition, so that, at present, all EU member states are in different stages of implementation of the EU's targets of green transition.

At the same time, both the United States and the European Union guarantee gender equality, individual identity, equal opportunities, social tolerance, and minorities' protection, so that the US and the EU represent the most open and diverse societies worldwide.

Above all, the US and the EU are at the very heart of global democracy, which is the only international order that provides the framework needed for the supporters of critical theories to manifest fully themselves and to develop according to their own agenda.

However, we cannot affirm that the critical approaches play a decisive role in shaping the behavior of the United States and the European Union within the international system, like in the case of realist and liberal approaches which define in many ways the EU' and the US' stance at the global level. On the other hand, critical approaches have a complementary value for the US and the EU as their domestic relevance indirectly reflects on their external policy. Examples in this regard are the common stances of the United States and the European Union against the abusive policies and actions perpetrated by autocratic and oppressive regimes towards the minorities, as well as the US – EU common support for international initiatives aimed at managing global warming, protecting the planet and ensuring the transit to green industry and development.

Conclusions

Having their origin in Frankfurt School for Social Research, critical perspectives appeared as a reaction to neorealist and neoliberal views on the world and put the individual in the center, at the expense of states and international organizations. Critical approaches focus on human instincts and natural characteristics, promoting the idea to use them as a basis to shape the society. Profoundly pessimist, critical theorists pay a particular attention to the perceived unjust and abusive behavior of state, authorities and majority groups against minority groups and individuals, and militate for strong resistance and activism in order to achieve the just treatment and the complete freedom of manifestation within the society in all its domains and at all its levels.

Constructivism and feminism are the most prominent critical schools of thought. Constructivists consider that the knowledge and the understanding of the

¹² United Nations, Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948, accessed at <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>

¹³ United Nations, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 1966, accessed at <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/cescr.pdf>

¹⁴ United Nations, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1967, accessed at

https://treaties.un.org/doc/treaties/1976/03/19760323%2006-17%20am/ch_iv_04.pdf

¹⁵ EU-US Summit 2021 – Statement – Towards a renewed Transatlantic partnership, accessed at <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/50758/eu-us-summit-joint-statement-15-june-final-final.pdf>

world represent a consequence of the individual interpretation, self-perception and perception of the surrounding environment. Therefore, they advocate for increasing self-awareness, resistance and engagement in the social and political life to prevent and counter any form of domination from any political or social actor. On the other hand, feminists credit the idea that enhanced representation of women in the management of international affairs will facilitate peace and stability and will lead to the attrition of masculine approaches marked by power in its material and military sense. During time, feminism developed beyond its initial agenda, overpassing *woman's liberation* central aim, pleading against the patriarch approach of education, policy and economy, and increasingly advocating for minorities' agenda, especially sexual orientation and gender identity related aims.

Critical perspectives represent eminently a Western theme that emerged, developed and manifests itself completely only in the United States and Europe. The EU and the US are strong supporters and protectors of the individual freedoms and rights and pay a particular attention to the individual autonomy, which are currently on the rise within both the American and European societies. Human rights and individual freedoms are at the core of US Constitution (the *Bill of Rights*) and the EU's build-up (*Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union, European Convention on Human Rights Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*). Moreover, the US and the EU are attached profoundly to the international law that guarantees and protects human rights and freedoms, namely the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*, the *International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights*, and the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*.

Moreover, topics of major interest for the supporters of critical theories, such as climate change, gender equality and equal opportunities, identity manifestation in all its forms, social tolerance, minorities protection, domestic security and environmental issues are high of the US' and EU's respective agendas.

At present, as reflected by the Statement of the US – EU Summit in June 2021 “*Towards a renewed Transatlantic partnership*”, both parties aim at achieving the common objectives to consolidate democracy, peace and global security and to protect the planet and sustain the green development. In this endeavor, the US and the EU promote initiatives and measures designed to responsibly manage climate change and lead the global effort in this domain by example.

All-important, the US and the EU are at the very heart of global liberal democracy, which is the only international order that provides the framework and the conditions to promote and advance the critical theories' agenda, as well the freedom of complete manifestation of their supporters.

We can conclude that the United States and the European Union identify themselves with the perspectives of the critical school of thought and this common

feature facilitates the development of the transatlantic partnership, serving as one of the many bridges connecting the two actors, as well as the European and American communities.

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